

A guide to analyzing spectral information from large sound files

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Last updated: 05/29/2021

The procedure

The purpose of this file is to document measuring spectral information from large sound files. The initial project for which this code was conceived contained 106,769 hours of long-term recordings. The method proposed here used FFmpeg in the command line prompt of windows to trim large (2 GB) files into many 3-minute files, starting at the beginning of each hour (code can be customized to make the starting period whenever the user wants). Then, we use R and some pre-built packages (tuneR and seewave) to calculate first and third quartiles, median frequency, and bandwidth (Q3-Q1).

Example sound files and an R markdown document can be found at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4267020>.

The steps:

- Download FFmpeg to your local machine (<http://ffmpeg.org/download.html>).
- Create a batch file in R for your files (see [Creating a batch file](#)).
- Run the batch file by opening it. It should automatically run.
 - this step takes the longest (computationally).
- Measure frequency variables from the remaining files (see [Measuring frequency values](#))

Creating a batch file

Instead of running the same line over and over again in cmd prompt, we will create a batch file that will allow FFmpeg to work on all your files sequentially, without any input from you.

```
setwd("C:/") # Set the working directory where the files are located

filenamesF <- dir(pattern="*.MP3", recursive=TRUE, full.names = FALSE) # This grabs the
# files within all subdirectories (recursive=T),
# and grabs the full path name (full.names=T)
filenames<-sapply(strsplit(filenamesF, "/"), tail, 1) # this grabs the last part
# of the string (just the file name without the path)
```

We will take a 3-minute recording from the middle of another file that ends in a timestamp with the following format: SITENAME_%Y%m%d_%H%M%S.MP3. SITENAME is a study-specific naming system (sites, species, etc.); then year, month, day; then time: _150000 is 15:00:00 or 3 PM (and 0 seconds and 0 milliseconds).

```
out=NULL
for(i in 1:length(filenames)){
  site<-data.frame(strsplit(filenames[i], "_"))
  filetime <- strptime(filenames[i], paste0(site[1,1],pattern="_%Y%m%d_%H%M%S.MP3"))
  # Take the time from the timestamp of the file
  site[,1]<-as.character(site[,1])
  hour<-as.POSIXlt(filetime)$hour # get the hour that the file starts

  for(j in 1:38){ # this is based on our sampling rate and file size of 2GB,
  # which shouldn't be able to give us more than 38 hours in one file.
  # Check a few files. If some are over 38 hours long, change this number here..

  hour<-hour+1 # this will add an hour each time through the loop
  if(hour>=24){site[2,1]<-as.numeric(site[2,1])+1 # this changes the date when hour = 24
  hour<-0} # and this changes the hour back to 0 for the new day
  hourC<-as.character(hour) # takes hour as a character
  if(nchar(hourC)==1){hourC<-paste0("0",hourC)} #adds a 0 in front of anything that
  # is only 1 character long, so it matches our timestamps
  hourStamp<-paste0("_",hourC,"0000") # turns hour into time stamp
  base <- strptime(paste0(site[2,1],hourStamp), "%Y%m%d_%H%M%S") # get the timestamp
  # that we want to extract
  dt<-difftime(base,filetime, units="secs") # get the time we need to go forward
  # with our file "filetime" to get to our designated time "base"
  # calculates time difference between starting created time stamp
  # and where the file name says its starting
  Td<-round(as.numeric(dt)) # just turns dt into a number (rather than a time object)
  # Td is our value to be used when creating the script
  # for our batch file for how many seconds
  # to go forward when extracting our 180 sec sample.

  type<-data.frame(strsplit(filenames[i], "\\."))
  type<-as.character(type[1,1])
  new<-strsplit(type, "_")[[1]] #splitting site date time

  ## Below is printing the code output for ffmpeg
  p<-print(paste(paste("ffmpeg -ss",Td,"-t 180 -i"),
  paste0(noquote(''),filenamesF[i],noquote('')),
```

```

        paste0("newfiles/short_" , new[1], "_", site[2,1], hourStamp, ".WAV")
      ), quote=F)
    out<-rbind(out,p)
    print(i)
  }}

```

Note: My preference is to put all the new shorter (3-min.) files (called ‘shorts’) into a new subdirectory that I call “newfiles” here. This keeps them separate from your original files. IF you do this, you must create a new folder manually (here called “newfiles”) in the parent directory, otherwise the batch file will not know where to put the new files.

ffmpeg options

Let’s dissect the batch code a bit by looking at one line:

```

ffmpeg -ss 22884 -t 180 -i "Folder1/CU2DF_20190626_223836.MP3"
                                newfiles/short_CU2DF_20190627_050000.WAV
#This code will come out as one line, but it is too long to visualize as such here.

```

ffmpeg activates the ffmpeg functions from within cmd.

The option `-ss` is starting at the rounded time difference that we specified to be the object `Td`, which is our time difference. `-t` is time interval, so 180 sec is specified here. So these two parts specify how far forward we go with each file, and then how long of a duration we grab.

The same information from the ffmpeg command line help file:

```

ffmpeg -help
  -t duration          record or transcode "duration" seconds of audio/video
  -ss time_off         set the start time offset

```

The option `-i` specifies that the next string will be the input files. Here we used the object `filenamesF[i]` to put the entire directory path and file name here, so that cmd can find the file. The space between the input file and output file will distinguish between the two.

Note that there are no quotes around the output path, but are around the input path. You need quotes if there are any spaces in path names (i.e. folder or file names), which some of the input paths had. We specified the output path ourselves here, so that we know there are no spaces.

Then, we write the table as a batch file so that it can just be opened and it will run in cmd.

```

write.table(out[,1], "test_180s.bat", row.names=FALSE, col.names=FALSE, quote = FALSE)

```

The options here are important to get the right formatting for the final file.

Empty files and file overwriting

As a last note, this code may try to create files past the end of the sound file. That is, a file will be written regardless of its size, so you may end up with a few small (essentially empty) files. Thus, in the next step, we remove files that are smaller than a threshold size.

Additionally, this code may try to create two files with the same name if you have files that are back to back. If you have a subsequent sound file, you may be asked whether or not you should overwrite the previous

(empty) file. When you run a batch file, you will be prompted to overwrite with a Y or N. You can manually enter one of these options for each instance, OR you can include `echo N|` or `echo Y|` to the beginning of the command prompt code. This will “echo” your response for every instance.

For example:

```
echo N|ffmpeg -ss 22884 -t 180 -i "Folder1/CU2DF_20190626_223836.MP3"  
                                newfiles/short_CU2DF_20190627_050000.WAV  
#This will not overwrite the first instance of the file named short_CU2DF_20190627_050000.WAV
```

Future improvements on this would be to dynamically assess which file (the already written one or the one to be written) has a larger size, and overwrite accordingly.

Measuring frequency values

We will now use existing methods to extract first (Q1), second (Median), and third (Q3) quartiles, and calculate a bandwidth variable that we define as Q3-Q1. We loop through all files to create a dataframe of values.

```
# Load required libraries after installing them:
install.packages("seewave")
install.packages("tuneR")
install.packages("stringr")
library(seewave)
library(tuneR)
library(stringr)

setwd("C:/Users/UserName/newfiles") # set wd to new folder

files<-dir(pattern="WAV$")
files<-files[-which(file.info(files)$size<=3000000)] # removes files that are too small
# or empty

SPEC<-NULL # This sets up an empty object, that we will fill with the for loop
FILE<-NULL # This is an empty character vector, where we will store our file names

for(i in 1:length(files)){
  noise<-readWave(files[i]) # read in the wav file, and store it as an object called `noise`

  dat<-acoustat(noise, fraction=50, wl=4096, xlim=c(0,4), plot=FALSE) # use acoustat to grab
# data from noise file
# multiply each quantity below by 1000 to put into Hz (instead of kHz) - personal preference
  Q1<-dat$freq.P1*1000 # store first quartile (Q1) as an object
  med<-dat$freq.M*1000 # store Median (second quartile) as an object
  Q3<-dat$freq.P2*1000 # store third quartile (Q3) as an object
  BW<-Q3-Q1 # create a bandwidth (BW) term, which we define as Q3 - Q1

  stat<-round(as.numeric(c(Q1, med, Q3, BW)),2) # round to 2 decimal places
  SPEC<-rbind(SPEC,stat)

  FILE<-rbind(FILE, as.character(files[i]))
  print(i)
}

SPEC<-cbind(data.frame(SPEC, stringsAsFactors = FALSE),
            data.frame(as.character(FILE),stringsAsFactors = FALSE))

colnames(SPEC)<-c("Q1", "Med", "Q3", "BW", "File") # rename columns

SPEC$Date<-str_split_fixed(SPEC$File, "_", 4)[,3] # pull date from file name
SPEC$SiteID<-str_split_fixed(SPEC$File, "_", 4)[,2] # pull Site from file name
SPEC$H<-str_split_fixed(SPEC$File, "_", 4)[,4] # pull time from file name

SPEC$Year<-strtrim(SPEC$Date, 4) # create year from date
SPEC$Mo<-substring(SPEC$Date, 5, 6) # create Month from date
```

```
SPEC$Day<-substring(SPEC$Date, 7, 8) # create Day from date  
write.csv(SPEC, "Spectrum180s.csv")
```